

Table continued

Variety	Damage score ^a	Variety	Damage score ^a
Nanjing 3714	3	Fu 8922	3
Shuangchao no. 25	1	Fu 8971	3
Fu 85-30	3	Dongtingzhengzhuru	3
Zhehu 102	3	Zhongguai	3
Zhehu 129	3	Ewan no. 3	3
Zhongyu 87-3	3	61 jing	3
6ET-198	3	17267	3
1673	3	Zhongxian 86-6	3
Zhongzuo 8531	3	Xianjing no. 1	3
Shun 44	1	HA79317-4	3
8810410	1	8807	3
Zhongyu 89-10	3	LS8713	3
88 Nan 14	3	85-183	3

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Feeding behavior of the brown planthopper (BPH) on susceptible and resistant rice cultivars

R. M. Hopkins, 8 Headlands, Kettering, Northants, NN15 7HP, United Kingdom

The feeding behavior of unstarved, newly molted, adult female BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål was assessed on single tillers of susceptible (IR22) and resistant (IR62) rice cultivars.

Ingestion patterns were electronically monitored using a direct-current system, which recorded voltage changes accompanying stylet activity within the plant. Sap ingestion was assessed by incorporating radioactive P into the rice plant and

monitoring the amount of label within the insect and its excretion after 24 h on the plant. Honeydew excretion was monitored simultaneously by slowly revolving the insect and plant so that honeydew droplets fell separately onto pH indicator paper.

Feeding behavior and weight change of *N. lugens* over 24 h on rootless rice tillers immersed in control and feeding deterrent solutions.^a

	Susceptible cultivar IR22			Resistant cultivar IR62
	Control (H ₂ O)	Beta-sitosterol (0.5% wt/vol)	Oxalic acid (0.5% wt/vol)	Control (H ₂ O)
Duration of phloem ingestion pattern (%)	7.5 a	16.0 a	0.3 a	1.6 a
Duration of xylem ingestion pattern (%)	35.3 a	22.9 a	6.8 b	33.3 a
Mean percentage weight change	17.8 a 2.8 a	-6.0 b -	- -31.3 b	-8.4 b -5.9 a

^aIn a row, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level (Mann-Whitney U test).

The total radioactivity of the insect plus excreted honeydew increased exponentially with ingestion pattern duration (see figure). Insects on the resistant cultivar followed the same logarithmic increase, but the total amount of label taken up was significantly less than that taken up by those on the susceptible cultivar.

We investigated the role of feeding deterrents (oxalic acid and beta-sitosterol) in relation to reduced sap ingestion from the resistant cultivar. Rootless tillers were immersed in 0.5% (wt/vol) solutions of either compound. Insect feeding behavior was monitored.

Both compounds induced significant insect weight loss with little influence upon the ingestion pattern duration. This affected the sap ingestion rate (see table). Either or both plant components may be responsible for the reduced sap ingestion and therefore resistance in rice cultivar IR62. □

Ln radioactive sap uptake (cpm)

Radioactivity of insect plus excreted honeydew in relation to total duration of ingestion patterns produced by *N. lugens* on susceptible IR22 (●), and resistant IR62 (○),